

Multilevel modeling for the analysis and prediction of school dropout: a systematic review

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This document is intended to present the protocol that was used to conduct the systematic literature review that was published in the IEEE 47th Computers, Software, and Applications Conference (COMPSAC) in 2023. The SLR was carried out during the first half of 2022 (from May to June).

1. Objective

The study aims to analyze primary literature studies, with the purpose of characterizing them, with respect to the models multilevel for the analysis and prediction of students at dropout risk, from the point of view of the researchers, in the context of scientific publications databases.

2. Research questions

The research questions are the following:

RQ1) Which are the main educational environments in which multilevel models were used for the analysis or prediction of school dropout?

Motivation: Provide the community in the field with an overview of the main educational environments in which multilevel modeling has been applied in the context of school dropout, intending to characterize them so that gaps and research contributions can be identified.

RQ2) What impact factors on school dropout have been investigated through multilevel models?

Motivation: Understanding what these factors are and how they affect school dropout can provide a more abstract view of the main points that need attention, providing support for decision-makers.

RQ3) Which are the most used multilevel models for the analysis and prediction of school dropout? RQ3.1) Were other artificial intelligence techniques used to support the multilevel approach?

Motivation: Characterize the multilevel models according to the educational environment in which they were used, in addition to verifying whether other artificial intelligence techniques were used in conjunction with the multilevel approach to improving the analysis and predictive capacity of the models.

3. Data sources for research

The search engines that we selected comprise a large part of the relevant journals and international conferences, such as: ACM Digital Library,

Engineering Village, Elsevier (ScienceDirect), IEEE Xplore, Scopus and Web of Science.

4. Keywords and synonyms

The language we used for research was English to contemplate a significant volume of studies in international literature. Therefore, we established a search string with the main keywords and synonyms related to the theme. As the review comprises primary studies that used multilevel models for the analysis and prediction of school dropout, we used “multilevel model” and “dropout” keywords and their synonyms to create the search string.

5. Search string

The established search string is presented in the following structure:

Search string: (((("multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("analysis" OR "model")) AND (("academic" OR "student") AND ("dropout" OR "evasion")))).

6. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The defined inclusion criteria (IC) and exclusion criteria (EC) are the following:

IC1: primary studies that present an application of a multilevel model for the analysis and prediction of school dropout.

EC1: the study refers to a technical report, a simple or expanded abstract, a slide presentation, a conference or workshop proceedings, a short paper, a secondary or tertiary study, a dissertation, or a thesis.

EC2: the language of the primary study is different from English

EC3: the full text of the primary study is not available.

EC4: the primary study does not meet IC1.

EC5: the primary study refers to an earlier version of a more up-to-date study on the same research, with the same authors.

7. Procedures for selecting primary studies

The procedures for selecting the primary studies comprise three stages: (i) the automatic search, which refers to the use of the search string in the search engines we selected to capture the first sets of studies; (ii) the first selection of primary studies, in which the selection criteria are applied when analyzing the title, abstract, and keywords of the studies; finally, (iii) the second selection of primary studies, in which we read the primary studies in full and apply the selection criteria.

- (i) Automatic search: for the collection of the first sets of studies, the search string will be used in all search engines, in addition to the inclusion of filters. The filters used in the automatic search comprise only the titles, abstracts, and keywords since they should include the main search terms.
- (ii) First selection of primary studies: this stage includes the identification of duplicate studies, which will be done with the support of the Parsifal.

Duplicate studies are recorded and discarded. Subsequently, the first analyzes are carried out on the set of studies collected by the automatic search. These analyzes include reading the titles, abstracts and keywords of the studies.

- (iii) Second selection of primary studies: this stage includes reading the full text of the primary studies identified in the first selection of studies. In addition, the selection criteria will be applied again, given that the reading of the primary studies in full may reveal some exclusion criteria.

8. String adaptation for each data source

The data sources and adaptations of the search string are presented in the following:

Data sources	Search string
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY((("multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("analysis" OR "model")) AND (("academic" OR "student") AND ("dropout" OR "evasion")))
ACM Digital Library	[[Abstract: "multilevel"] OR [Abstract: "hierarchical"] OR [Abstract: "nested"] OR [Abstract: "mixed"] OR [Abstract: "random coefficients"]] AND [[Abstract: "analysis"] OR [Abstract: "model"]] AND [[Abstract: "academic" OR [Abstract: "student"]]] AND [[Abstract: "dropout" OR [Abstract: "evasion"]]]
IEEE Xplore	((("Abstract": "multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("Abstract": "analysis" OR "model")) AND (("Abstract": "academic" OR "student") AND ("Abstract": "dropout" OR "evasion")))
Web of Science	TS=((("multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("analysis" OR "model")) AND (("academic" OR "student") AND ("dropout" OR "evasion")))
ScienceDirect	Title, abstract, keywords: ((("multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("analysis" OR "model")) AND (("academic" OR "student") AND ("dropout" OR "evasion")))
Engineering Village	found in Compendex & Knovel for 1884-2022: ((("multilevel" OR "hierarchical" OR "nested" OR "mixed" OR "random coefficients") AND ("analysis" OR

	"model")) AND (("academic" OR "student") AND ("dropout" OR "evasion"))
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